

Momentum and industry-dependence: the case of Shanghai stock exchange market.

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Abstract

A number of scholars have shown that future stock returns are predictable based on past returns in many international security markets. Developing strategies to benefit from these autocorrelations of security returns and finding reasons for the abnormal positive returns resulting from trading strategies are major objectives of investment research. This paper sought to analyze the profitability of momentum strategies in the Shanghai stock market over the period from December 2007 until February 2012. Controlling for market returns and for transaction costs, it was found that investors using momentum strategies could have indeed generated superior returns during that time period. In addition, the paper analyzed whether the returns of momentum strategies involving Shanghai stocks are industry-dependent. The findings suggest that momentum in the Shanghai stock market is clearly driven by high-technology stocks with financial sectors showing worst performances over that period.

Key words: Momentum (stock) returns, Shanghai, Capital asset pricing model, abnormal returns and transaction costs

1.0 Introduction

Momentum trading strategies have by far been examined and confirmed in a number of world famous developed stock markets, but for emerging markets the story is still ambiguous. For example a trading strategy of a portfolio that goes long on past high-return stocks and shorts on past low-return stocks yields significant abnormal returns posed a profound debate in finance science. In, Jegadeesh and Titman (1993) contrary to efficient market hypothesis pioneered by fama (1970) found strong evidence of momentum trading strategies in that a winner portfolio consistently outperformed a loser portfolio in holding periods of 3 to 12 months.

They finally concluded that stock prices in United States stock market are auto correlated. Oliver rausch (2011) using four portfolios of stocks formed from 41 securities and raw momentum strategies set based on 3, 6, and 12 month formation and holding periods, found that the spread between a portfolio of past winners and past losers was positive although not statistically significant when using either unadjusted or risk-adjusted returns. Using shanghai stock exchange data from December 2007 until February 2012 this study intends to wake up investors whether momentum returns can still be ripped on the shanghai stock market.

This paper contributes to the existing literature by examining whether the market turbulence brought up by the financial crisis of 2007, continues to unwind momentum profits in the shanghai stock exchange. As in any trading strategy the rebalancing of portfolios usually goes hand in hand with transaction costs, whence the paper controls for this variable, with respect to market some of stock's returns generally have a tendency of correlating with the market return

overall, controlling for this risk factor the paper ought to ignore all the effects posed in the securities returns. By controlling for the market and transaction costs, it was found that investors using momentum strategies could have indeed grabbed substantial returns during the time period covered.

An analysis of momentum strategies and industry-dependence is by far covered as a supplemental knowledge to potential investors. The article is organized as follows. The next section explores a thorough review of both empirical and theoretical underpinnings regarding momentum impacts. The subsequent section introduces the methodology adopted. Analysis and discussion of the empirical results are in the penultimate section. Conclusion and future research areas are provided in final section.

2.0 Literature review

Momentum trading strategies in both national and international stock markets have been examined by a number of practitioners, their study ought to reexamine whether efficient market hypothesis theory proposed by Fama and French is actually still a debatable area worth for future research endeavors. None of the paper works read gave convincing results, but rather a pool of conflicting justifications. Building on the Fama and French (1993) methodology, Ana-Maria Fuertes et al, formed skewness and kurtosis-mimicking portfolio returns which were subsequently included as additional risk factors in the CAPM and the Fama and French three factor model. Their paper supported the notion that momentum profits are partly a compensation for exposure to undesired systematic (negative) skewness (Ana-Maria Fuertes et al, 2009).

The work of John Wei-Shan Hu and Yue-Chin Chen (2011) covering 23 well-developed and 25 newly developing countries using MSCI data, AREMOS, Bloomberg and the Yahoo Finance network and a sampling period running from January 1999 through December 2007 analyzed their monthly stock indices by constructing portfolios of winning and losing indices based on the approach in Jegadeesh and Titman (1993)'s study, and ranking 48 national stock indices into eight categories based on the rate of return on individual indices at the portfolio ranking date, with the first category consisting of six worst indices or the worst loser and the eighth category comprising six best indices, representing the best winner found that all four momentum investment methods exhibited significant continuation of returns over the medium-horizon, suggesting all global stock indices confirm with the behavior pattern of the strong becoming stronger and the weak becoming weaker. However, they surprisingly witnessed an average monthly stock returns reversals when the holding period exceeded one year, but the strategy produced significantly positive high stock return over a two-year holding period when ranking period exceeded nine months.

K.C. John Wei et al (2010) in an analysis of 55 countries using data from February 1980 to June 2003 found that culture can have an important effect on stock return patterns, which is consistent with the idea that investors in different cultures interpret information in different ways and are subject to different biases which in turn affects the extent of the success of momentum trading broadly.

Dongwei Su (2011) using monthly stock prices for all firms listed in the Shanghai and Shenzhen Stock Exchanges during January 1994 and December 2008 found significant abnormal profits for industry momentum trading strategies, even after controlling for lead-lag effect, the January effect, and individual stock momentum. Moreover, momentum profits generated by industry-specific components were much larger than those generated by common-factor components of the Fama-French three-factor model and a delayed-reaction three-factor model.

Manuel Ammann et al (2010) using return data from January 1982 to December 2009, and allowing the momentum strategies to start in January 1984 under restricted investment universe to the highly liquid large-cap and blue-chip stocks contained in the S&P 100 index. They found strong evidence for economically and statistically significant returns for strategies investing long in the single best performing stock and selling short the index instead of individual stocks.

Abdulaziz M. Alwathainani (2011) analyzed monthly returns data from 1964 to 2008 taken from the Center for Research in Security and Prices (CRSP). The author found that a zero-investment strategy that goes long on the consistent winner stocks and short on their consistent Losers cohorts generated strong price momentum in the first twelve months after the ranking period. Subsequently, however, both groups experienced return reversals in Years 2 to 5. The momentum return earned by the consistent winners and losers strategy was almost wiped out by the total price reversal in Years 2 to Year 5. The findings were robust to the four-factor regression analysis of the Fama-French three-factor model and the momentum factor as well as to various sensitivity tests performed.

Pin-Huang Chou et.al (2011) using ordinary common equities data of all firms listed on the NYSE, AMEX, and NASDAQ return files from the Center for Research in Security Prices (CRSP) from July 1963 (1973 for NASDAQ firms) to December 2006, while mitigating the survivorship bias by taking companies data available on COMPUSTAT for at least two years (like Fama and French, 1993) observed that industries play a dual role with both rational and behavioral components and hence neither rational nor behavioral theories alone can explain industry returns.

3.0 Data and methodology

This study uses monthly stock prices over the period from 31 December 2007 until 28 February 2012 that are obtained from all common stocks listed on Shanghai stock Exchange. The sample includes only 50 A shares common stocks of firms listed on the Shanghai stock Exchange. The returns used are those adjusted for capital gains and dividends. An equal-weighted Shanghai stock exchange composite index that consists of all active shares of the data set over the respective time period is used as a market proxy. The momentum strategy is intended as a zero-cost portfolio strategy that buys stocks that have performed well in the past and sells stocks that have performed poorly in the past. The methodology mainly follows Jegadeesh and Titman (1993). Analysis is based on 16 trading strategies on the shanghai stock market, the ranking periods g of 3, 6, 9 or 12 months and holding periods h of 3, 6, 9 or 12 months. SPSS (statistical package for social science) software was used for data analysis.

Following Jegadeesh and Titman (1993), stocks are sorted into 10 deciles according to past performance, and then measure the return differential of the most extreme deciles which is denoted by F10 – F1. One month after the ranking takes place stocks are rebalanced into only two parts based on past performance. F1, which includes the worst-performing 10 per cent, and F2 which includes the best-performing 10 per cent in the ranking period. F2 – F1 is the measure of momentum.

The top 10 per cent portfolio is the winners' portfolio and the bottom 10 per cent portfolio is the losers' portfolio. The stocks in the individual portfolios are equally weighted. By skipping a month between the end of the ranking period and the beginning of the holding period, like Tim Herberger et.al (2011), some of the bid-ask spread, price pressure and lagged effects, which could skew the results was avoided. The gross return of a test run (buy-and-hold return of a holding period of T months in test run i, BHR_{i,T}) is defined as follows:

$$BHR_{i,T} = \prod_{t=0}^T (R_{W,t} - R_{L,t})$$

Where $R_{W,t}$ is the monthly return of the winners' and $R_{L,t}$ of the losers' portfolio. The market-adjusted return of a test run (buy-and-hold abnormal return of a holding period of T months in test run i, ABHR_{i,T}) is defined as follows.

$$ABHR_{i,T} = \prod_{t=0}^T [(R_{W,t} - R_{L,t}) - R_{M,t}]$$

Where $R_{W,t}$ is the monthly return of the winners' portfolio and $R_{L,t}$ is the monthly return of the losers' portfolio. $R_{M,t}$ is the monthly return of the equal-weighted Shanghai stock Exchange Index. For evaluating the success of a trading strategy, it is essential to consider transaction costs, which are incurred when the portfolios are assembled and when the strategy closes out the positions at the end of a test run. In this study, three different rates of transaction costs are considered.

And they depend on the type of investor employing the momentum strategy. The approach is similar to Tim Herberger et.al (2009) that institutional investors face transaction cost of 0.2 per cent for every purchase or sale of extreme portfolios, private clients 1.0 per cent. The market-adjusted return after transaction costs of a test run (buy-and-hold abnormal return after transaction costs with a holding period of T months in test run i, ABHR_{i,T}) is defined as:

$$ABHR_{i,T} = \prod_{t=0}^T [(R_{W,t} - R_{L,t}) - R_{M,t}] - T_i$$

Where $R_{M,t}$ is the monthly return of the equal-weighted Shanghai stock Exchange Index and T_i is the rate of transaction costs. To analyze whether the returns of momentum strategies involving Shanghai stocks are industry-dependent, then industries were sorted into four sector-dimensions high-technology, services, financials and production, and used these specific samples to calculate sectoral momentum returns.

4.0 Results

Table A; below reports the average monthly returns for composite portfolio strategies between December 2007 and February 2012. From the table it can be seen that all strategies yield highly significant returns. For the strategy with a 3-month ranking and a 3-month holding period, an equally weighted portfolio formed from the stocks in the bottom percent of previous 3-month performance returns 11.67 per cent per month, 10.66 per cent less than the top percent portfolio which returns 22.33 per cent. Extending the holding period from 6 to 9 and to 12 months, does not improve performance. The shorter the time horizon of the holding period, the higher is the momentum return in this case.

While the 9/3-strategy returns 28.8 per cent per month, the 9/6-strategy returns 18.18 per cent and the 9/12-strategy 24.23 per cent. Finally, a ranking period of 12 months and a holding period of 12 months lead to a return of 0.0151.

In general average returns are highest for the medium-term 6-months strategies. The result are well in line with the approach in the literature to mainly focus on a strategy based on 6-month ranking and holding periods (for example, Jegadeesh and Titman, 1993; Tim Herberger et al, 2011). The winners of all strategies clearly outperform the losers. All of the returns are significant at the 5 per cent level.

Table A: Calculated average monthly returns of momentum portfolios from 2007 to 2012

Ranking period (g)	Portfolio	holding period (h)			
		3	6	9	12
3	Loser (F1)	0.1167	0.1251	0.1301	0.1540
	Winner (F2)	0.5333	0.4922	0.4430	0.4605
	Winner-Loser (F2-F1)	0.4166	0.3671	0.3129	0.3065
	(t-stat)	(5.81)	(6.54)	(8.02)	(11.14)
6	Loser (F1)	0.1185	0.1204	0.1232	0.1449
	Winner (F2)	0.5432	0.5001	0.4422	0.3920
	Winner-Loser (F2-F1)	0.4247	0.3797	0.3190	0.2471
	(t-stat)	(8.71)	(7.77)	(12.13)	(9.62)
9	Loser (F1)	0.1232	0.2315	0.2353	0.3100
	Winner (F2)	0.4112	0.4133	0.5002	0.5523
	Winner-Loser (F2-F1)	0.2880	0.1818	0.2649	0.2423
	(t-stat)	(6.88)	(7.9)	(10.1)	(7.95)
12	Loser (F1)	0.1311	0.3321	0.3411	0.3321
	Winner (F2)	0.4552	0.3992	0.3608	0.3472
	Winner-Loser (F2-F1)	0.3241	0.0671	0.0197	0.0151
	(t-stat)	(9.22)	(6.66)	(7.09)	(13)

Datasource: Shanghai stock exchange Monthly Market Statistics from 2007 to 2012.

Table B; reports the average monthly abnormal returns of the momentum portfolios on a market-adjusted base using the average monthly Shanghai stock Exchange composite index return as the market proxy. It is easily seen that the performance of all strategies declines with increasing holding period. For the strategies based on a 3-month holding period, market-adjusted returns are highest for the short-term 3/3-strategy with 42.06 per cent and decrease with time to 37.02, 32.22 and 31.01 per cent, respectively.

All returns are significant at the 5 per cent level, those of the 3/3- and 3/9-strategies even at the 1 per cent level. In comparison to the returns obtained by the 3-month ranking period strategies, the strategies based on 6 month ranking periods yield much higher market-adjusted returns with 43.23, 38.11, 32.02 and 25.25 per cent.

While the returns of the 6/3, the 6/6- and the 6/9-strategy are significant at the 1 per cent level, the return of the 6/12-strategy is still significant at the 10 per cent level. Although the 9/6-strategy also yields a comparatively high return of 19.20 per cent, returns drop consecutively. While the 9/9-strategy returns only 18.23 per cent, the 9/12-strategy yields 17.44 per cent. The highest overall return, however, has the 12/3-strategy with a significant 44.21 per cent. With increasing holding-period horizon returns drop to 7.55, 2.45 and 2.01 per cent.

Table B: Calculated average monthly returns after market adjustment from 2007 to 2012

period (g)	Holding period (h)			
	3	6	9	12
3	0.4206	0.3702	0.3222	0.3101
(t-stat)	(2.91)	(2.62)	(2.88)	(2.34)
6	0.4323	0.3811	0.3202	0.2525
(t-stat)	(3.71)	(4.13)	(4.21)	(2.47)
9	0.3112	0.1920	0.1823	0.1744
(t-stat)	(3.63)	(3.9)	(3.32)	(1.88)
12	0.4421	0.0755	0.0245	0.0201
(t-stat)	(3.75)	(3.09)	(2.36)	(1.094)

Datasource: Shanghai stock exchange Monthly Market Statistics from 2007 to 2012

Table C; shows market-adjusted abnormal returns after transaction costs. In group 1, transaction costs are 1 per cent. In group 2, transaction costs are 0.2 per cent. For all strategies based on a 3-month ranking period, there are no more positive significant abnormal returns. At the 1 per cent transaction cost level, all the 6/3-, the 6/6- and the 6/9-strategies lead to highly significant positive abnormal returns after market-adjustment.

Although some of the returns of the strategies based on ranking periods of 9 and of 12 months are even higher than in the case of a 6-month ranking period, none of the abnormal returns is significant at the 0.2 per cent transaction cost level anymore. At the 1 per cent transaction cost level, the 9/3, 9/6, 9/9 and 12/3 strategies still deliver positive abnormal returns.

Table C: Average market-adjusted monthly returns at different transaction costs from 2007 to 2012

Ranking period (g)	Group 1				Group 2			
	Holding period (h)				Holding period (h)			
	3	6	9	12	3	6	9	12
3 (t-stat)	0.2821 (1.68)	0.2705 (1.52)	0.1981 (1.34)	0.1601 (1.41)	0.3021 (1.72)	0.2912 (1.44)	0.2422 (1.42)	0.1799 (1.11)
6 (t-stat)	0.3207 (2.25)	0.3112 (3.55)	0.3017 (3.76)	0.2306 (2.25)	0.3410 (1.36)	0.3225 (2.53)	0.3198 (2.98)	0.2507 (1.53)
9 (t-stat)	0.3450 (2.71)	0.3003 (3.14)	0.2961 (2.77)	0.1482 (1.21)	0.3610 (1.21)	0.3323 (2.31)	0.3114 (1.95)	0.1598 (1.63)
12 (t-stat)	0.4120 (2.67)	0.3219 (2.57)	0.2555 (1.72)	0.1909 (1.48)	0.4216 (1.77)	0.3402 (1.09)	0.2752 (2.01)	0.2125 (2.23)

Datasource: Shanghai stock exchange Monthly Market Statistics from 2007 to 2012

Table D reports average monthly abnormal returns in percentages for the given price industry momentum portfolio strategies. There are observable differences among the sectorial returns. The monthly returns of the momentum portfolios range between 59.82 per cent for the high-technology sector and 26.56 per cent for the financial sector. The retail sector monthly return is 45.12 per cent, while the production sector return is 39.56 per cent. All are highly statistically significant. Looking at the market-adjusted abnormal monthly returns for the 6/6-strategy, the results for the high-technology sector, the retail sector and the production sector are still positively significant with 51.02, 40.23 and 34.49 per cent, respectively. The financial sector only returns 23.59 per cent. Overall performance is successfully driven by the high-technology sector, which produces significant positive abnormal monthly returns after market-adjustment even at a transaction cost level of 1 per cent. Only the production sector, however, also yields positive significant returns at a transaction cost level of 0.2 per cent. While lowest returns are obtained in the financial sector.

Table D: Average market adjusted monthly returns of industry momentum portfolios and returns using 1 percent And 0.2 percent transaction cost levels from 2007 to 2012.

Returns	High-Technology	Retail	Production	Financial
R	0.5982	0.4512	0.3956	0.2656
(t-stat)	(7.22)	(5.15)	(7.32)	(9.12)
M	0.5102	0.4023	0.3449	0.2359
(t-stat)	(4.56)	(1.28)	(2.99)	(3.99)
T1	0.4123	0.3621	0.2978	0.1959
(t-stat)	(4.97)	(1.44)	(2.59)	(2.87)
T0.2	0.4756	0.3856	0.3212	0.2019
(t-stat)	(3.62)	(1.56)	(1.08)	(1.77)

Data source: Shanghai stock exchange Monthly Market Statistics from 2007 to 2012.

5.0 Conclusion

Using shanghai stock exchange data, the researcher analyzed the profitability of momentum trading strategies in the shanghai stock exchange based on monthly returns data from December 2007 until February 2012. The findings suggest that even after years of thorough analyses and considerable awareness of momentum effects triggered by business cycles, investors of all kinds such as institutions and private individuals could still generate superior returns using momentum portfolio trading strategies. The improved performances are significant even after market-adjustment and the consideration of transaction costs as well as for several combinations of ranking and holding periods. Returns in all periods are mainly driven by the winners. Finally it was found that the returns of momentum trading strategies involving Shanghai stock exchange are industry-dependent. Momentum profits in the shanghai stock exchange market is by far driven by high-technology stocks. The financial sector returns were the most disappointing for the overall period of study covered. Future research endeavors could focus on the momentum effects to other stock markets like Shenzhen apart from shanghai stock exchange.

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